

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PHENOTYPIC AND GENOTYPIC METHODS FOR DETECTION OF METHICILLIN-RESISTANT STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS

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Abstract

Background: Methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) has been emerged as a nosocomial and community acquired pathogen worldwide. There are many challenges for laboratory detection of MRSA. The aim of this study was to compare different phenotypic methods with PCR based method as a gold standard for detection of *mecA* gene. **Methods:** A total of 158 clinical isolates of *S. aureus* isolated from various clinical specimens over the period of 1 year in Sharda Hospital, Greater Noida, were included in our study. Methicillin resistance was determined by cefoxitin disks, oxacillin screen agar, Automated Vitek -2 compact, results of these methods were compared with *mecA* gene based PCR method as a gold standard method. **Results:** Among 158 isolates from *S. aureus*, 59 (37.47%) isolates were positive for *mecA* gene by PCR method. Cefoxitin disk diffusion method identified 58 isolates as MRSA with *mecA* gene +. The results of cefoxitin disk diffusion method when compared with PCR method has sensitivity of 98.3% and the specificity of 97.9%. Oxacillin agar medium has 100% sensitivity and 94.9 % specificity. Vitek-2 compact has sensitivity of 96.7% and 97.9% specificity respectively. **Conclusion:** Result of cefoxitin disk diffusion method with 98.3 % sensitivity and 97.9% specificity is comparatively more precise to PCR method for detection *mecA* gene in MRSA than any other phenotypic method. Cefoxitin disk diffusion method can be considered as an alternative phenotypic method of PCR for detection of MRSA.

Keywords: Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus, *mecA* Gene, Oxacillin Screen Agar.

INTRODUCTION

S. aureus is one of the major causes of hospital and community-acquired infections, resulting in serious consequences. It can affect the bloodstream, skin and soft tissues, and lower respiratory tract and can cause infections related to medical instrumentation, such as central-line associated bloodstream infection (CLABSI), as well as infections ranging from trivial skin diseases to fatal septicaemia (1). Currently, 90 to 95% of *S. aureus* strains worldwide are penicillin resistant, with the plasmid encoded penicillinase readily transferable via transduction or conjugation (2). MRSA is defined as a strain of *S. aureus* that is resistant to a large group of antibiotics called β -lactams, that includes penicillin's and cephalosporins. The incidence of MRSA varies from 25 per cent in western part of India to 50 per cent in South India (1,3). MRSA in most cases accounts for at least 25 to 50% of *S. aureus* infections in hospital settings.

Accurate and early laboratory detection of MRSA is also important for institution of appropriate antibiotic treatment and also for the prevention of the spread of infection to other

patients and health care personnel. There are several phenotypic methods such as cefoxitin disc diffusion, MIC determination [by agar dilution, broth dilution and Etest], oxacillin screen agar (OSA) method and latex agglutination test for PBP2a, for detection of MRSA(4).

The performance of phenotypic methods in the detection of methicillin resistance is inconsistent, time consuming and also encounters difficulties in detecting all the resistant isolates. Presently, PCR for the amplification of the *mec-A* gene is considered the gold standard for detecting methicillin resistance in *S. aureus* (5). Cefoxitin is a better inducer of *mec-A* gene and disc diffusion test using cefoxitin gives clearer endpoints and is easier to read than tests with oxacillin with its comparable accuracy to PCR(6). This study attempts to evaluate various Phenotypic and Genotypic methods for the identification of MRSA.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A Prospective cross-sectional study was conducted in the Central laboratory, Department of Microbiology, SMS & R, Sharda Hospital, Greater Noida, India for a period of 1 year. During the study, a total of 158 strains of *S. aureus* were isolated from various clinical samples. Isolates were identified on the basis of the colony and microscopic morphology, catalase, tube coagulase testing, deoxyribonuclease agar, and growth on mannitol salt agar (7). All isolates were stored in glycerol broth at -80°C until further use.

Detection of MRSA by phenotypic methods

1. Cefoxitin Disk Diffusion Test

Disk diffusion method using cefoxitin discs (Hi-media) was performed for all isolates on Mueller–Hinton agar for detection of MRSA as recommended by CLSI guideline (8). Briefly four to five isolated colonies from overnight growth of *S. aureus* on Blood agar was suspended into 4-5 ml of saline solution. The turbidity of suspension was adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard turbidity and inoculated on Mueller–Hinton agar plates. The zone of inhibition for cefoxitin disk was measured and by referring to CLSI guidelines reported as MRSA or methicillin susceptible *S. aureus* (8).

2. Oxacillin screen Agar

Oxacillin resistance screen agar base used for MRSA detection was prepared according to manufacturer's instructions (Hi Media Pvt. Limited, India). To perform the oxacillin screen test, a swab dipped in 0.5 McFarland's suspension of the isolate was deposited as a spot on the agar surface and it was incubated at 35°C for 24 h. Any growth even one colony after 24 hours, indicated that the isolate is methicillin (oxacillin) resistant. No growth indicated that the organism is susceptible to methicillin and oxacillin.

3. Colorimetric identification and antibiotic sensitivity of *Staphylococcus* species by Vitek™ 2 compact system

All preliminary identified isolates of *S. aureus* (MSSA and MRSA) were tested by Vitek™ 2 compact system (BioMe'rieux, France) according to the procedures provided by the company. Identification and Antibiotic Susceptibility test results of the organism were obtained after 12-

18 hours. The Antimicrobial Susceptibility test result identified the isolates as *S. aureus* with positive cefoxitin screen test, thus labelling them as MRSA. Unlike directly testing with oxacillin, the Vitek 2 system uses cefoxitin as the primary indicator antibiotic to detect MRSA due to its higher sensitivity in identifying resistant strains.

Quality strain: The quality control strains including methicillin resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA ATCC 43300)

Detection of the *mecA* Gene by Polymerase Chain Reaction

All the phenotypically detected MRSA strains were then subjected to Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of *mecA* gene. In our study, Genotypic method (PCR) was performed for confirming and comparing it with various phenotypic methods for detection of MRSA.

The bacterial DNA was extracted using the method provided by the kit manufacturer (Qiagen Mini), DNA thus extracted, was stored at -80°C for further PCR amplification.

PCR Amplification:

Firstly, the cooling block was pre-cooled at 4° C in a Refrigerator or Deep Freezer. The desired number of PCR tubes as per the number of samples to be run in one PCR cycle were placed into the Cooling Block. At least one negative control (water, PCR grade) and positive control were included per PCR run. Depending upon the number of samples, following pipetting and PCR scheme for preparation of amplification mixture was used.

Table 1: Pipetting scheme for PCR Master Mix (as per Kit Literature)

MRSA MASTER MIX	1rxns.	10rxns.
MRSA Super Mix (R1)	12 µl	120 µl
MRSA Mg. Sol. (R2)	2.5 µl	25 µl
IC-1 (R3) RG	0.5 µl	5 µl
Total	15 µl	150 µl

Table 2: General Data Interpretation and Analysis of PCR Results:

CHANNEL	FAM	HEX	RESULT
A	Signal detected	Signal detected	MRSA detected
B	Signal Not detected	Signal detected	MRSA Not detected
C	Signal detected	Signal Not detected	PCR inhibition, re extract the sample and repeat PCR
D	Signal Not detected	Signal Not detected	PCR inhibition, re extract the sample and repeat PCR

Observation & Results

The culture samples for the study were derived from patients of all age and sex who attended the hospital's out-patient department or were admitted to the hospital and showed signs & symptoms of infection. Total number *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates included in the study were 158.

Table 3: Distribution of MRSA and MSSA among Staphylococcus aureus isolates

Methicillin Susceptibility	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
MSSA	99	62.66
MRSA	59	37.34
Total	158	100

In our study 28 (47.46%) of the MRSA isolates were hospital acquired MRSA while 31 (52.54%) were community acquired.

Table 4: Distribution of Hospital acquired and Community acquired MRSA

	Number	Percentage (%)
Community Acquired MRSA (CA-MRSA)	31	52.54
Hospital Acquired MRSA (HA-MRSA)	28	47.46
Total	59	100

Phenotypic & Genotypic Methods for Detection of MRSA

For the detection of methicillin resistance, all the 158 isolates of Staphylococcus aureus were subjected to Cefoxitin disk diffusion method, Oxacillin screen agar, Vitek-2 compact and real time PCR for mec-A gene detection. Due to some constraint issues, isolates subjected to VITEK-2 compact cefoxitin screen were 78 only. PCR for mec-A gene detection was considered as the gold standard method for detection of methicillin resistance in Staphylococcus aureus isolates for this study. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value and negative predictive value were calculated for all the phenotypic methods of MRSA detection.

PCR for the detection of MRSA

Out of the total of 158 Staphylococcus aureus isolates, mec-A gene was detected by real time PCR in 59 isolates (37.34%) and the remaining 99 (62.66%) were negative for mec-A gene. PCR was considered the gold standard method for identification of MRSA in this study. Hence, the performance of all the other phenotypic methods for the detection of MRSA were evaluated and compared against PCR for mec-A gene.

Phenotypic Detection

1. Cefoxitin disk diffusion method identified 60 isolates as MRSA and 98 as MSSA. When compared to mec-A gene detection by PCR, 2 cefoxitin resistant isolates were mec-A negative (false positive) and 1 cefoxitin sensitive isolate was mec-A positive (false negative). The sensitivity of cefoxitin disk diffusion method was 98.3% and the specificity was 97.9%. The positive predictive value of the method was 96.6% and the negative predictive value was 98.9%.
2. Out of the 64 isolates showing growth on OSA, mec-A gene was detected in 59 isolates, hence the OSA results were false positive for 5 isolates. However, mec-A gene was not detected in any of the 94 isolates reported as MSSA by oxacillin screen agar. The sensitivity of oxacillin screen agar was calculated to be 100% and the specificity was 94.9%. The positive predictive value of this method was calculated at 92.2% and the negative predictive

value was 100%.

3. Out of these 78 strains 30 were mec-A positive (by PCR) and VITEK-2 correctly detected 29 of these isolates as MRSA with 1 false negative result. By PCR 48 strains were mec-A negative, 47 of these were correctly reported as MSSA by VITEK-2 and there was one false positive result. The sensitivity of VITEK-2 was found to be 96.7% and the specificity was 97.9%. Positive and negative predictive values of VITEK-2 for the detection of MRSA were 96.7% and 97.9% respectively.

Table 5: Results of phenotypic methods and their correlation with mec-A gene detection

Rt-PCR (Genotypic Isolates)	Cefoxitin Disc Diffusion (30µg) (n=158)		Oxacillin screen Agar(6µg/ml) (n=158)		Vitek-2 compact (n=78)	
	R	S	+	-	R	S
mec-A (+) (59)	58	1	59	-	29	1
mec-A (-) (99)	2	97	5	94	1	47

On comparing negative predictive values, oxacillin screen agar showed the best NPV of 100% while cefoxitin disc diffusion and Vitek-2 compact were at 98.9% and 97.9% respectively. (Table 6)

Table 6: Comparison of phenotypic methods for detection of MRSA against mecA gene detection by PCR (Gold standard)

Test Method	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
Cefoxitin Disc diffusion	98.3	97.9	96.6	98.9
Oxacillin Screen Agar	100	94.9	92.2	100
Vitek 2 compact	96.7	97.9	96.7	97.9

The results obtained by all the three phenotypic methods namely cefoxitin disc diffusion, oxacillin screen agar and Vitek-2 compact were analyzed for statistical significance using Fisher's exact test and P values were calculated

When Fisher's exact test was applied to compare the outcomes of cefoxitin disk diffusion method with oxacillin screen agar, the two tailed P-value was 0.7297. Thus, the differences in the performance of cefoxitin disc diffusion and oxacillin screen agar were statistically not significant. (Table 7)

Table 7: Comparison between cefoxitin disk diffusion and oxacillin screen agar by Fisher's exact test

Method	MRSA	MSSA	Total	P-value
Cefoxitin disc diffusion	60	98	158	0.7297
Oxacillin screen agar	64	94	158	

The results of Cefoxitin disk diffusion method were compared to Vitek-2 compact using the Fisher's exact test. The P-value obtained was 1.0000, indicating no statistically significant difference. (Table 8).

Table 8: Comparison between cefoxitin disk diffusion and Vitek-2 compact by Fisher's exact test

Method	MRSA	MSSA	Total	P-value
Cefoxitin disc diffusion	60	98	158	1.0000
Vitek-2 compact	30	48	78	

The results of Oxacillin screen agar were also compared to Vitek-2 compact using the Fishers exact test. The P-value obtained was 0.7794, indicating no statistically significant difference between the two methods (Table 9)

Table 9: Comparison between Oxacillin screen agar and Vitek-2 compact by Fisher's exact test

Method	MRSA	MSSA	Total	P-value
Oxacillin screen agar	64	94	158	0.7794
Vitek-2 compact	30	48	78	

DISCUSSION

The present study included a total of 158 isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*. We identified 59 (37.34%) of these as MRSA and 99 (62.66%) as MSSA. A study published in 2011 by Indian Network for Surveillance of Antimicrobial Resistance (INSAR) group, was conducted in 15 Indian tertiary care centers and reported a similar prevalence of MRSA at 40% (6-9) Arora S et.al (98-10), in their study from Punjab reported a slightly higher prevalence of 46% while the prevalence was 38.4% in a study by Tiwari HK from Uttar Pradesh (99-11). In our study the prevalence of MRSA was higher in males (54.9%) as compared to females (45.1%). And the highest prevalence was seen in the age group of 15 45 years (56%). Similar to our study, another study by Kulshrestha A. et al 2017 from India, reported higher MRSA prevalence in males (73%) and most commonly affected age group was 21-30 years (101-12). Among all antibiotic classes, glycopeptides emerged as the most sensitive class of antibiotic against MRSA. All MRSA isolates showed 100% sensitivity to Vancomycin and Teicoplanin, followed by Linezolid (98.3%) and Amikacin (62.7%).

Positive results of direct MRSA testing should always be confirmed by a culture method or a second molecular test. For laboratories with high false-positivity rates or in regions with low prevalence of MRSA, confirmation is essential (57-13). PCR for the amplification of the *mec-A* is presently considered the gold standard for the detecting methicillin resistance in *S. aureus* (106-14). In comparison to gold standard method of PCR, many authors have recommended that cefoxitin could be a surrogate marker for the detection of methicillin resistance in the settings where PCR is not feasible, as it is a better inducer of *mec-A* gene and disc diffusion test using cefoxitin gives clearer endpoints. In the present study we evaluated different phenotypic methods for detection of MRSA taking PCR for *mec-A* gene as the gold standard. *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates included in this study were subjected to cefoxitin disc diffusion, oxacillin screen agar, VITEK-2 compact cefoxitin screen test and *mec-A* gene detection. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated for all the phenotypic methods used in the study.

Table 1: Results of Cefoxitin disc diffusion test- Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV and NPV by various studies

Author	Year	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
Panda RK et al (106)	2016	96	100	100	98.5
Demir T et al (108)	2016	98.7	97.5	95	99.3
Sharma S et al (107)	2017	100	100	100	100
Present study	2024	98.3	97.9	96.6	98.9

The differences in results of the test by various studies can be due to variation of testing conditions, like temperature, duration of incubation, preparation of inoculum and pH, thickness of medium for Antibiotic susceptibility testing.

Table 2: Results of Oxacillin screen agar test -Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV and NPV results by various studies

Author	Year	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
Panda RK et al (106)	2016	95.1	100	100	97.8
Demir T et al (108)	2016	100	96.9	93.9	100
Sharma S et al (107)	2017	98.07	97.80	96.36	98.89
Present study	2024	100	94.9	92.2	100

As different studies have shown a range of results, this can be because Oxacillin screen agar is a sensitive media and requires meticulous preparation of media, as oxacillin is extremely sensitive and media is sensitive to the temperature and duration of incubation (107-15)

Table 3: Results of Vitek-2 compact cefoxitin screen test Sensitivity and Specificity by various studies

Author	Year	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Roisin S et al (115)	2008	97.5	100
Junkins AD et al (116)	2009	99.1	99.4
Present study	2024	96.7	97.9

In the present study, the differences of the results of various phenotypic methods when compared to mec-A gene detection by PCR were not found to be statistically significant (P value>0.05).

CONCLUSION

Detection of mec-A gene by polymerase chain reaction is considered as the best method to detect MRSA. However, cefoxitin disk diffusion test, which is a simple and cost-effective method has shown high sensitivity and specificity. Thus, it can be used as an accurate surrogate marker in routine testing to detect MRSA.

We hope that this study will serve as a useful reference for clinical microbiologists, physicians and other researchers interested in the study of prevalence, antibiotic susceptibility pattern and comparative performance of various phenotypic and genotypic methods for detection of MRSA.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests.

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